

Adopting the disciplinary data archive services and adapting to the needs of the institution

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<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- FDV established in 1961
- In 1966 two research centres were established
 - Centre for Public Opinion Research
 - Centre for the Study of Cooperation with Developing Countries
- 25 research centres in 2016
- 100 researchers in 2018

Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- 1997
- Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
 - 600 social science surveys in a data catalogue
 - cca. 700 users yearly (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- Member of [CESSDA ERIC](#)
- Trusted repository certification
- Involved in EU projects

 ADP Social Science Data Archives
<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/eng/>
CTS Certification 2017-2019

ADP's mission and role

Is a national infrastructure that:

- collects **important data sources** from a wide range of social sciences, interesting for analyzing Slovenian society;
- Deposits and preserves these data;
- Promotes their further use for scientific, educational and other purposes.

HOW TO GET DATA?

FIND →

REGISTER

→ ANALYZE

HOW TO DEPOSIT DATA?

RECORD →

PREPARE

→ DEPOSIT

Open data and RDM activities

- ADP involved on national and international level:
 - ✓ [National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#)
 - ✓ [Action Plan of the National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#)
- Providing support
 - ✓ Developing training materials, tools, services
 - ✓ Consulting researchers
 - ✓ Organizing Workshops, webinars, lectures
 - ✓ Attending conferences
 - ✓ ...
- Target audiences
 - ✓ Researchers
 - ✓ Librarians
 - ✓ Decision makers
 - ✓ Publishers

Motivation to deal with RDM and OA policy

In 2015, after an unsuccessful investigation of a case of suspected data fabrication, the faculty management initiated the establishment of institutional-level RDM policy

Challenges:

- Institutional control over the research data produced by its research staff
- Provide access to data by the institution management
- Moving towards the open data principles (EU level) →

Research data Pilot (H2020):

Motivation to deal with RDM and OA policy

„Rules on the organization and implementation of research activities at the Faculty for Social Sciences“ (adopted in 2017)

- Article 16: ADP takes care about longterm curation of data collected by researchers employed at FDV
- Article 26: RD created by FDV employees are to be as open as possible
- Article 43:
 - researchers obliged to deposit original data and related material at ADP
 - Rules on RDM and procedures for researchers to be developed

Working group for RDM

- Established in 2017 by a dean
- Members → researchers, data repository staff, a librarian, IT and a data expert from technical field

Mission:

- Guidelines for researchers
- Action plan for the faculty

Minimising the time and effort needed to meet the administrative requirements of the guidelines (time and cost efficient procedures)

Working group challenges

Forms and rules to be developed on:

- Managing internal / institutional records on research data
- Managing internal data repository
- Procedures and measurements on assessing data quality and depositing data with ADP

Integrate:

- Researchers' needs
- Institutional needs
- ADP's services and infrastructure

Open questions

Researchers

- A large variety of research data
 - ✓ type (qualitative, quantitative),
 - ✓ research purpose (from pilot studies to large-scale studies),
 - ✓ methodological quality,
 - ✓ funding (from publicly funded research projects to commercial studies) and
 - ✓ contractual provisions for data handling (e.g. some data are under strict NDA policy).
- Long tail data

ADP

- Selection and quality assesment measurements

→ Self-depositing service is being implemented

Open questions

Institutional level:

1. Internal institutional data repository (IDR) plays only an intermediate role? For a limited time period
2. IDR is place to store data, which cannot be shared outside the group:
 - Who will take care for data curation on a longterm?

Thank you!!!

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